

Road Damage Detection Using Image Enhancement Techniques

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Abstract—This paper investigates the impact of image enhancement techniques for road damage detection using the YOLOv8n object detection model. A sample of 2,000 images extracted from the RDD2022 dataset was used to evaluate CLAHE, Gaussian Blur, and Brightness Adjustment. The results showed that CLAHE achieved the best overall performance by improving Precision, F1-Score, mAP@50, and mAP@50-95 compared with the baseline model.

Index Terms—Road damage detection, YOLOv8n, image enhancement, CLAHE, Gaussian Blur, Brightness Adjustment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Road infrastructure plays a critical role in transportation systems as it impacts traffic safety, travel speed, and public service delivery. But road surfaces are subject to repeated traffic loads, weather variations, ageing and other environmental factors, which cause various types of road damage, including cracks, potholes and deformation. Without timely monitoring and maintenance of these damages, they will grow worse over time, requiring higher maintenance costs, negatively affecting passenger comfort and safety [7].

The conventional road damage inspection process typically relies on manual inspection by engineers or road maintenance personnel. While manual inspection can be effective, it is labor-intensive, expensive and impractical for frequent inspection of large road networks. Manual inspection can also be subjective and presents a safety hazard to workers. For these

reasons, computer vision-based road damage detection is a growing field of research in smart transportation systems.

Recent research has demonstrated that deep learning models, particularly YOLO-based object detection networks, can be used to detect road damage as they can detect and localize damaged regions in images with bounding boxes. For instance, Li et al. developed RDD-YOLO, a road damage detection model based on an improved YOLOv8, and demonstrated that YOLO-based models can be used to detect a variety of road damage such as longitudinal cracks, transverse cracks, alligator cracks, repairs, and potholes. This research demonstrates the value of adopting deep learning for more accurate and efficient road damage detection.

But object detection models' performance can be compromised by poor image quality. Poor illumination, low contrast, shadows, blurriness, noise, and varying image resolutions are some of the problems that can occur with road images. These factors can affect the visibility of cracks and potholes, which may affect the performance of the YOLO model in detecting damaged areas. As a result, image processing techniques can be used before detecting road damage to enhance the visual quality of the road images and highlight features that represent road damage.

The dataset used in this project is obtained from Kaggle.com, an online platform that provides open datasets for artificial intelligence, machine learning, model training, and

data analysis. Kaggle is valuable for data science projects as it provides researchers and students with access to open data, notebooks, and the opportunity to apply machine learning algorithms to real-world problems. In this project, Kaggle is used for obtaining road damage images with examples of cracks and potholes. The images are used as the source for applying image enhancement methods, and then using the YOLO model on the original and enhanced images. The use of Kaggle as a data source helps the project to deliver a practical computer vision task with real image data input.

In this project, we employ a number of image processing methods prior to using YOLO for road damage detection. First, all images are resized to the same dimension. Next, Gaussian Blur is used to reduce noise and blur out unwanted details. Next, Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization is applied to enhance the local contrast and make the damage regions stand out. Once the images are enhanced, YOLO is applied to identify and locate road damage such as cracks and potholes.

The key aim of this project is to compare the detection effects of YOLO algorithm on original and enhanced road images. This can then be used to assess the effectiveness of image enhancement in improving detection performance and facilitating the recognition of road damage. In summary, this project uses image processing and deep learning to assist with more precise, efficient and automated road damage detection.

II. PROJECT GOALS AND OBJECTIVES

A. Project Goal

The objective of this project is to design an automatic road damage detection framework based on image enhancement and a deep learning model (YOLO). The goal of this project is to enhance the detection of potholes, longitudinal cracks, transverse cracks and alligator cracks from road images. Road images can suffer from low illumination, blurring, shadowing, low contrast and noise, so image enhancement algorithms will be used prior to model training and testing to enhance the visibility of potential damage features and help the model to achieve better detection. This project is concerned with the integration of conventional image processing and object detection. The developed system will aid in the efficient inspection of roads compared to manual inspection, which can be tedious, expensive, and prone to human errors.

B. Objectives

- To choose and prepare an appropriate road damage dataset including common damages like potholes, longitudinal cracks, transverse cracks and alligator cracks.
- To use image preprocessing and enhancement methods like resizing, contrast adjustment, CLAHE, brightness change, and noise removal to enhance the features of road damage.
- To develop a YOLO-based road damage detection model that can detect different types of road damages in original and enhanced images.

- To assess the difference in performance of YOLO on original and enhanced images to determine the impact of image enhancement on detection accuracy.
- To enhance the model's generalization ability with data augmentation techniques such as rotation, flipping, blur, noise, and brightness variations to mimic actual road environment.
- To assess model performance in terms of precision, recall, F1-score, mean Average Precision (mAP) and inference time.
- To evaluate the model with low illumination, blur, shadows and low contrast to determine its effectiveness.

C. Performance Criteria

The project aims to:

- Enhance the appearance of the road damage.
- Obtain better results from YOLO detection on enhanced images than on original images.
- Achieve reasonable precision, recall, F1-score and mAP.
- Provide acceptable inference speed for road inspection.
- Determine the most suitable image enhancement technique for road damage detection.

III. RELATED WORKS (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Research on road damage detection has been ongoing, moving from initial dataset building to advanced deep learning architectures, and recently to integration with image enhancement.

One of the key datasets in this area was introduced by Maeda et al. [1] who created the Road Damage Dataset (RDD) which was gathered using mobile phone cameras on public road networks. They showed that a CNN can be scaled up to detect surface defects such as cracks and potholes at scale. The dataset and models, however, were only applied to raw, non-processed imagery, and the impact of image preprocessing was not explored.

A later research used YOLOv5 for a multi-class road damage classification task, testing it on a real-world dataset of seven different road damage categories that achieves an accuracy of around 92% for detecting damage and can make inferences in real time [2]. The results presented here showed that single-stage detectors are suitable for this task, but the study was limited to the architecturally assessing the detectors and not to the influence of pre-processing or image quality degradation on detector performance under real-world challenging conditions.

Zeng and Zhong [3] proposed a lightweight version of YOLOv8 using channel attention mechanisms and depthwise separable convolutions to reduce computational requirements and enhance detection accuracy. The model outperformed the baseline of YOLOv8n in terms of accuracy and efficiency. However, the increase in performance was blamed solely on the changes in the architecture and not on image enhancement as a complementary method on the upstream side.

Aina et al. [4] extended the detection task using YOLOv8 to a real-world operational environment, training and testing

on the RDD2022 dataset and testing in real video streams with an accuracy of around 80%. All experiments were performed with unprocessed input images in this study, and the ability of the system to withstand low lighting, blur, and noise was not considered. This research validated the deployment of YOLO-based pipelines for road monitoring but all experiments were performed for input images which were not processed.

This is why the literature is so much focused on architecture rather than the impact of preprocessing on detection accuracy, as explored by Pham [5] in their work. Contrast limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE), gamma correction, brightness adjustment, and noise reduction techniques were applied before the inference on deep learning based detectors. Results of the study showed measurable gain in image clarity and visibility of features in the low-light, noisy acquisition environment, where better inputs led to better detection robustness and overall accuracy of the detection result than the unprocessed baseline. This work directly inspires the proposed pre-processing pipeline in the present work.

The work of Li et al. [6] introduced a pavement damage detection framework Cycle-YOLO, which combines Scharr edge enhancement, Laplacian pyramid sharpening, and CycleGAN-based image translation with the backbone of YOLOv5. Overall, the hybrid method enhanced the visibility of the crack boundaries and the detection of small defects under complex lighting and surface conditions, with 88.2% mAP@0.5. The results of this study reflect that there is significant improvement in performance when using enhancement-detection co-design, especially for fine-grained damage categories like hairline and transverse cracks.

Silva et al. [8] proposed an automated road damage detection approach using UAV images and deep learning techniques. Their study involved evaluating three different models: YOLOv4, YOLOv5, and YOLOv5 with a Transformer Prediction Head, as well as YOLOv7, which leverages RDD2022 images and a Spanish road dataset. The results indicated that YOLOv7 performed the best in terms of mAP@0.5, demonstrating the effectiveness of YOLO-based models for road damage detection in real road monitoring scenarios. The direct effect of image enhancement techniques like CLAHE, gamma, and noise, reduction, however, was not systematically investigated, but the work primarily centered around the comparison of the deep learning models and UAV-based data acquisition.

Jeong and Kim [9] tackled the problem of road damage detection by tiling images of roads with multiple sources and then using YOLO. Their work is valuable, because images from the road can have different resolution, origin, and recording circumstances, particularly when it comes to the road images originating from different countries and devices. They selected high-resolution images and applied image tiling in their processing and trained several YOLOv5x models to form an ensemble framework. Their approach successfully enhanced the detection accuracy on multi-source road images, but the study was primarily conducted on the issues of tiling and ensemble learning rather than exploring the impact of

contrast enhancement, brightness correction, and denoising of road images on the visibility of cracks and potholes prior to YOLO detection.

A. Gap Analysis

The literature examined contains a number of frequent limitations such as focusing on model architecture, dataset expansion, tiling and ensemble strategies as the key approaches to enhance the accuracy of road damage detection, while less research has systematically explored the impact of image quality preprocessing on model performance. Despite the fact that studies [1]– [4] and [8] and [9] collectively advance the technical concept of a YOLO-based road damage detection system from raw road images, UAV images, and multi-source datasets respectively, they all concentrate more on the development of the detection models rather than the effect of the preprocessing on detection performance. More specifically, the effects of low illumination and occlusion, blur and shadows as well as low contrast and noise, typical of road acquisition environments, have not been adequately quantified.

Research [5] and [6] indicate that measurable improvements can be achieved using enhancement-based approaches. However, the amount and manner in which improvement is achieved depends on the type of enhancement and type of detection approach. To address this, the current study adopts a structured image enhancement pipeline consisting of Gaussian blur, CLAHE, and brightness adjustment before passing the images to the YOLOv8 for the inference and tests the results with unprocessed images while also measuring performance with precision, recall, F1-score, and mAP in a controlled manner.

IV. DATA ACQUISITION AND PREPROCESSING

In this project, we use the Road Damage Detection 2022 (RDD2022) dataset from Kaggle as the main data source. The original dataset contains around 38,000 road images collected from different countries under various road and environmental conditions. However, a subset of 2,000 images was selected for this project to reduce training time and computational requirements while maintaining sufficient data for model development and evaluation. The images include different types of road damage such as potholes, longitudinal cracks, transverse cracks, and other surface defects. The dataset is organized into training, validation, and testing sets, and each image is provided with bounding box annotations indicating the location and type of road damage. Before training, all images were resized to a fixed resolution of 640×640 pixels to ensure consistency during processing. Several image enhancement techniques were tested, including Gaussian Blur, brightness adjustment, and Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE). Gaussian Blur was used to reduce noise, while brightness adjustment was applied to improve image illumination. However, these techniques did not produce satisfactory detection results. CLAHE achieved the best performance by enhancing local contrast and making road damage features more visible, especially in low-contrast areas.

Therefore, CLAHE was selected as the final preprocessing method used in this project. These preprocessing steps helped improve image quality and enhanced the overall performance of the YOLOv8n road damage detection model.

V. MODEL DEVELOPMENT AND TRAINING

A. Model Development

The YOLOv8n object detection model was selected for road damage detection. YOLOv8n is a lightweight and fast object detection model to identify and localize road damages like cracks and potholes using bounding boxes. The pretrained parameters were used for the model initialization and the model was fine-tuned with the RDD2022 dataset.

B. Image Enhancement Technique

Several image enhancement techniques were evaluated to improve road damage visibility before training the model. The techniques tested here were CLAHE (Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization), Gaussian Blur and Brightness Adjustment.

Experimental results demonstrated that the CLAHE was the most effective enhancement method, which enhanced image contrast in the local regions and made more noticeable the damage features in the roads. A few more tests were performed with the mixture of CLAHE, Gaussian Blur and Brightness Adjustment. It did not, however, help the model performance when compared with the use of CLAHE alone. Hence, CLAHE is chosen as the pre-processing method in the proposed system.

C. Training Process

The enhanced dataset was generated by applying CLAHE to all training, validation, and testing images while preserving the original annotations.

The YOLOv8n model was trained using:

TABLE I
TRAINING PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Epochs	50
Image Size	640 × 640
Batch Size	16
Pretrained Weights	yolov8n.pt

After training, the best model weights were automatically selected and evaluated using the validation set.

D. Performance Improvement

The results show that applying CLAHE improved Precision, F1-Score, mAP@50, and mAP@50-95. This indicates that enhancing image contrast helped the model distinguish road damage features more effectively.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT

Metric	Baseline	Enhanced
Precision	0.332	0.480
Recall	0.359	0.342
F1-Score	0.345	0.400
mAP@50	0.322	0.354
mAP@50-95	0.152	0.167

VI. EVALUATION AND ANALYSIS

The evaluation was carried out on the YOLOv8n model both before and after applying image enhancement techniques. The road images or preprocessed images were used as the baseline model and enhanced model, respectively. The enhanced version used the following main enhancement technique, CLAHE, and an experiment was performed that included a preprocessing chain of CLAHE, Gaussian Blur, and Brightness Adjustment. The validation set was used for the evaluation process and the size of the images and the model settings were kept as it was used in the validation set.

A. Evaluation Metrics

Precision: Number of correct road damage detections made. The higher precision is the lower number of false detections.

Recall: Number of actual road damages that the model identified. The higher the recall rate, the fewer damages that are missed.

F1-Score: A single measure of precision and recall.

mAP@50: It computes the accuracy of detection at 50% IoU threshold.

mAP@50-95: A more stringent metric since it tests the model at multiple IoU levels between 50% and 95%.

Inference time: The time taken by the model for inference is crucial for real-time road inspection systems.

B. Quantitative Results

The following table shows the results that have been produced by the baseline model, the CLAHE enhanced model and the model that combines both of these enhancements. The main enhanced model is the CLAHE-only model that was found to have the highest overall performance of the tested enhancement models.

C. Results Analysis

The model that used CLAHE performed best overall. The precision was improved from 0.331945 to 0.480452, consequently, the model was more reliable with the prediction of road damage. This improvement is indicative of the fact that CLAHE has sharpened potholes and cracks due to local contrast enhancement, which is actually an improvement, as a result, the model made fewer false detections.

The F1-Score also improved from 0.344979 to 0.399845. This indicates that the overall rate of correct detections and those which were missed became more positive following CLAHE. The mAP@50 increased from 0.322407 to 0.353876, and the mAP@50-95 increased from 0.152113 to 0.166993.

TABLE III
COMPARISON OF BASELINE AND ENHANCED YOLOV8N VALIDATION RESULTS.

Metric	Baseline YOLOv8n	CLAHE YOLOv8n	CLAHE + Blur + Brightness
Precision	0.331945	0.480452	0.273445
Recall	0.359078	0.342400	0.351096
F1-Score	0.344979	0.399845	0.307443
mAP@50	0.322407	0.353876	0.282260
mAP@50-95	0.152113	0.166993	0.142057

The improvements indicate the model was able to better detect and localize road damage using CLAHE.

However, recall decreased slightly from 0.359078 to 0.342400. This implies the CLAHE model was better able to detect the damages, but it was unable to detect some of the damages in the baseline. This is an important observation because enhancing contrast could make some of the damages more visible, but it could also alter the pattern of weak, or very small, cracks in a way that makes them more difficult for the model to detect.

The enhancement experiment that combined CLAHE, Gaussian Blur and Brightness Adjustment did not improve the model. It, however, does not match the baseline and CLAHE-only in terms of lower precision, F1-Score, mAP@50 and mAP@50-95. Though it was slightly higher than the CLAHE-only model, it didn't lead to an overall improvement. This is probably because Gaussian Blur filters out small cracks, and brightness adjustment can alter the texture of roads. Often, the cracks are thin and small, and too much processing can lose valuable information that the model needs but does not provide.

These results suggest that the enhancement technique that is best for this project is CLAHE. It enhanced the most crucial detection metrics, while maintaining a simple preprocessing pipeline. The results also demonstrate that the more enhancement steps one added does not necessarily lead to better performance. All preprocessing methods need to be examined, as certain methods can dampen out damage features of importance.

D. Further Considerations and Potential Improvements

The results are moderate, but the CLAHE model improved the results. In part, this is because the project focused on a subset of the RDD2022 data. A larger, more balanced set of images would be helpful for the model to learn more examples of each damage type, particularly those classes with fewer images. The validation results also indicate that certain damage classes may be more difficult to identify than others, particularly in the case of small or thin cracks.

Possible future work involves adjusting the confidence threshold, increasing the number of training epochs, and using more severe data augmentation techniques, or trying other techniques for improvement such as sharpening, denoising filters, adaptive gamma correction or edge enhancement. It could also be worth comparing YOLOv8n with larger models like YOLOv8s or newer versions of YOLO to see if the restriction is due to the model size or image quality.

Lastly, for each setting of the preprocessor, inference time should be measured. Processing time per image was good at baseline validation, which could be an additional processing cost for the enhanced pipelines. In this regard, future tests shall include the detection accuracy as well as the processing time for the total test to verify the system's usefulness for the real road inspection.

VII. CONCLUSION (AND FUTURE WORK)

This paper focuses on the impact of image enhancement techniques for road damage detection on the YOLOv8n object detection model. We experiment using a sample of 2,000 images extracted from RDD2022 dataset to see if any of the enhancement techniques would provide a better result for detecting road damages (such as cracks and potholes). We experimented with 3 different image enhancement techniques, namely CLAHE, Gaussian Blur, and Brightness Adjustment.

According to the experiment, it appears that CLAHE is the best image enhancement technique amongst the ones we have tested. When compared to the baseline model that was trained with original images, the model that was trained with CLAHE-enhanced images showed better performance for Precision, F1-Score, mAP@50 and mAP@50-95. It proves that contrast enhancement could increase the detectability of the features of road damages, thus improving the object detection performance. Nevertheless, by combining CLAHE with Gaussian Blur and Brightness Adjustment, the improvement was not added, which implies more complicated preprocessing could have negative effect to the detection.

Even though the detection performance is at a moderate level, the paper proved that image preprocessing can enhance the performance in limited dataset. The results show that image quality is an influential factor in deep learning based road damage detection, and a simple image enhancement method like CLAHE can benefit the model without changing its architecture.

In future studies, we could train on much larger datasets or even a more complete set of images. There are many other image enhancement techniques to test, and we could consider different object detection architectures too. Further evaluation can be done under various real-life circumstances and road conditions to find a robust way to deal with the problem.

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